

Exploring the Interconnection between Chakras and the Nervous System through the Buddhist Meditation Approach and a Revised Understanding of the Chakras System

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Abstract: The purpose of studying the cosmic power in the spiritual life protocol using the Buddhist meditation approach is to understand the interplay between the seven chakras and the transfer and exchange of energy between the human body and the environment. The chakras serve as the main funnel for this energy exchange. This connection is commonly referred to as the mind-body connection and is related to psychoneuroimmunology (PNI), which involves the immune, nervous, and stress systems. Although the seven Chakras have widely recognized, their precise locations are not well-established in most studies and not easy to growth and energy controlled. The Chakras 1-7 were found to be positioned in the body cavity and directly related to the nervous system, with only Chakra 1 and Chakra 2 emitting red and orange light at the start of meditation, which later changed to white light upon reaching meditation absorption level 4. Overall, the Buddhism meditation method, Anapanasati practice, proved useful in Chakras development and the relationship of Chakras system, Nervous system and the Caduceus symbol were presented.

Keywords: Chakras, meditation, cosmic power, nervous system, Caduceus.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to much previously reported research, meditation is very important for human life and brain development, as it can lead to the expression of gamma and delta waves (Thomus and Cohen., 2014; Deolindo et al., 2020; Nash and Newberg., 2023). These brain waves have been shown to be indicators of good emotional quotient (EQ) and intelligence quotient (IQ) development in individuals (Nash et al., 2013; Thomus and Cohen., 2014; Tang et al., 2015; Dorjee, 2016; Khoury et al., 2017; Sevita et al., 2017; Millière et al., 2018; Deolindo et al., 2020).

In the context of Chakra studies for spiritual and cosmic power, meditation is a method for activating, developing, and controlling energy. The Chakras system is a concept in alternative medicine and spirituality that is believed to relate to the flow and balance of energy in the body. The anatomical location and characteristics of the 7 Chakras have been documented for over a millennium (Sevita et al., 2017; Chhabra et al., 2019; Moga, 2022).

The First Chakra, also referred to as Root Chakra/Muladhara/Kundalini, is situated from the reproductive organs to the anus and was strongly linked with emotions such as aggression, sexuality, and anger. The malfunctioning of organs in the vicinity of the first Chakra is also associated with this energy center. Additionally, it is believed to be related to the hot and cold snake souls, with the recognized symbol for this Chakra being the color red.

The second Chakra, also known as the Sacral Chakra or Swadhisthana, is located in the lower abdomen and is represented by an orange symbol. It is believed to be connected to sexual and creative energies and was closely related to the first Chakra. The third Chakra, or Solar Plexus Chakra/Manipura, was located at the naval and is represented by a yellow symbol. It was considered a vital point for life and energy flow, involved in breathing and healing, and related to emotions such as power, confidence, and willpower.

The fourth Chakra, known as the Heart Chakra/Anahata, is represented by a green symbol and is located at the center of the chest. It is considered to be related to emotions of love, compassion, and empathy, as well as the health of internal organs.

The fifth Chakra, or Throat Chakra/Vishuddha, is located at the pharynx and is represented by a light blue symbol. It is believed to be connected to communication and self-expression, and imbalances may result in conditions such as tonsillitis, hyperthyroidism, and overactive thyroid

The sixth Chakra, or Third Eye/Ajna, was represented by a dark blue symbol and is located at the forehead. It is believed to be related to intuition, insight, and perception, as well as commonly and specialist intelligences.

The seventh and final Chakra, known as the Crown Chakra or Sahasrara, is represented by a violet symbol and is located at the top of the head. It is considered to be a special Chakra, linked to spiritual and cosmic consciousness and believed to be related to mental illnesses such as Alzheimer's symptom (Jalil et al., 2015; Chhabra et al., 2019; Moga, 2022).

While the Chakra system is not scientifically proven, many people find it helpful for spiritual and personal growth. It is important to note that any physical or mental health concerns should be addressed by a licensed healthcare professional. In recent times, there has been a growing interest among people in the use of meditation techniques such as Yoga, Reiki, Tai Chi, and cosmic power for the enhancement of physical and mental health, as well as for spiritual growth (Ahn et al., 2008; Nash et al., 2013; Thomus and Cohen, 2014; Kaur and Singh., 2015; Dorjee., 2016; Millière et al., 2018; Chhabra et al., 2019; Deolindo et al., 2020; Condon and Makransky, 2020).

However, mastering meditation techniques is not an easy task, as it requires control over the energy flow in the body. Moreover, the positions and functions of the 7 Chakras have not been well-established, and are based on limited case studies and reports. Thus, the goal of this paper is to propose a method for locating the Chakras associated with the nervous system, utilizing the Buddhist meditation approach and its distinct features.

The aim of this paper is to propose a methodology for identifying the locations of the chakras in relation to the nervous system, utilizing the unique features of the Buddhist meditation approach with an emphasis on activity.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Method

This is a description of a meditation technique using the Anapanasati practice in the context of the Tipitaka and the paracanonical Pali texts. The practice involves focusing on the breath at three different locations, namely the nose tip, chest, and abdomen, in order to develop mindfulness and concentration (Thomus and Cohen, 2014; Millière et al., 2018; Nash et

al., 2013; Deolindo et al., 2020; Nash and Newberg., 2023). These three locations correspond to the positions of Chakra 6, Chakra 4, and Chakra 3, respectively.

Once a sense of calm has been achieved through this practice, the focus shifts to the abdomen, specifically for the purpose of developing Chakra 3. The next step is to cultivate a sense of detachment or freedom from emotions by observing the breath without attachment or aversion. This level of practice, which involves the loss of the sense of breathing, is considered the highest level or level 4 of the Anapanasati practice.

When Chakra 3 has been mastered, the practitioner may then move on to focusing on each chakra position in turn, as described previously (Jalil et al., 2015; Chhabra et al., 2019; Moga, 2022). Overall, the goal of this meditation technique is to cultivate mindfulness and concentration, as well as a sense of detachment or emotional freedom.

Results

The Anapanasati practice has the ability to present the positions of the chakras. The first study identified Chakra 3, which is located in the abdomen above the navel inside the body cavity, as described above.

The second study focused on Chakra 6, also known as the Third Eye, traditionally located at the forehead (Jalil et al., 2015; Chhabra et al., 2019; Moga 2022). This study found that Chakra 6 is not directly presented at the physical Third Eye position, but rather inside the brain or possibly at the middle of the head. This position is believed to provide a good balance of mindfulness, energy force, and the ability to sustain level 4 meditation for an extended period of time.

So, the comparison of the Nervous system and a new Chakra 6 position is used for these studies because the role of the Chakras system is suggested to have a very close relationship with the nervous system, especially in terms of function.

When the new methodology was tested against the nervous system comparison, the results showed that the position of the Chakras are located in the cavity of the body and in a straight alignment corresponding to the brain and spinal cord label system (Fig. 1). Chakra 1 is located in the S3 position, in the area of the coccygeal spinal nerve, pudendal nerve, and sacral plexus, and concerned to inferior hypogastric plexus was described by Sevit et al. in 2017.

Its activity is related to the Sympathetic and Parasympathetic systems and closely related to the most commonly presented emotions such as active emotions, sexuality, reproductive organs, buttocks, bladder, prostate gland, legs, ankles, feet, toes, and most metabolism, which is closely related to the pineal gland and hypothalamus or Chakra 6. The dysfunction of this chakra could cause symptoms such as constipation, bladder problems, diarrhea, and numbness in the legs.

Chakra 2 is recognized as being presented at L5-S position of the nervous system with functions that partially overlap with Chakra 1 and Chakra 3, corresponding to the reproductive organs, buttocks, groin, thighs, colon, large intestine, knees, legs, and feet.

Chakra 3 is very important as it is the middle of the human body and is involved in 'the flower of life' as described in the Emerald Tablets book (Steele and Singer, 1928; Holmyard, 1929; Holmyard, 1957; Needham, 1980; Williams, 2016;). Meditation focusing is difficult, but breathing energy is stabilized, making it safe and easy to control and maintain a large amount of energy. It is located inside the cavity of the body, straight to the navel and the lumbar spinal nerve L3-L4 positions. This chakra is functionally related to chakra 2, such as reproductive organs and the colon, legs, feet, and so on.

Chakra 4 or Heart chakra corresponds to the Thoracic spinal nerve and the thymus gland, which are located at T6-T7. It covers organs around the heart such as lungs, chest, arms, esophagus, larynx, trachea, gallbladder, liver, diaphragm, stomach, pancreas, spleen, kidneys, small intestine, appendix, adrenals, colon, uterus, and buttocks.

Chakra 5 is located at the junction of the right and left clavicle bones, or cervical spinal nerves, to the thoracic spinal nerve, as C8-T1. Its function corresponds to the thyroid gland, tonsils, eyes, intracranial blood vessels, lacrimal gland, parotid gland, scalp, base of the skull, neck muscle, diaphragm, shoulders, bowels, arms, wrists, hands, fingers, esophagus, heart, lungs, and chest.

The third-eye chakra, or Chakra 6, is located in the forebrain, in the thalamus area. However, when meditation is focused on the hypothalamus position, the energy of breath is transferred to the pineal gland and pituitary gland, which affects the opening of the third eye. Therefore, the name of this chakra does not change. The pineal gland has been found to be highly sensitive to light, and even brief daily exposure to intense light can help alleviate symptoms of Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD).

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The pineal gland may be a vestigial remnant of a third eye that was once possessed by our distant reptilian ancestors. Despite its location deep within the brain, the pineal gland is remarkably sensitive to light. The light can reach the pineal gland through the ears, as the gland is situated at a level near the ear hole. The gland is composed of translucent tissue and is located near the carotid canal and several nerve pathways into the brain, which could allow light to diffuse along these paths without being obstructed by bone. In this state, indigo blue light can be activated by the ear.

Chakra 6 is functionally involved in body temperature, blood pressure, hunger and thirst, the fullness eating sensor, sexuality, mood, sleep, and most metabolisms with the help of the nervous system. However, the position of Chakra 6 affects all parts of the brain because the examination found that the energy or white light expanded and covered the head.

The last chakra is the Crown Chakra, or Chakra 7, located at the sulcus of Rolando and the center of the skin sensation in the brain. It covers the top of the skull cranium.

When meditation and breath energy are focused on Chakra 7, a gold light will be presented, and it will open for connection with the energy outside the body. The lotus flower's photography will be presented, and the gold light will automatically transfer to Chakra 6, Chakra 1, and lastly, Chakra 3. This process will result in comfortable and good emotions.

III. CONCLUSION

The results of these studies, which utilized the fourth absorption from Anapanasati practice, are enough to support the notion that the chakras system has a very close relationship with the nervous system, with the same role, function, and corresponding position in comparison. In addition, most people think of the meaning of the old Caduceus symbol, the wand of Hermes, or the Esclapius staff, which is used for pharmaceutical and healing purposes (Shetty et al., 2014; Prakash and Carlton Johnny., 2015; Hamann and Martalon., 2016; Güner et al., 2019; Katsaras et al., 2020; Kamodi et al., 2020).

However, the answers are not so clear. When we compare it with the nervous system and the chakra system, it is revealed that the circle at the top of the staff represents Chakra7. The two wings represent the right brain and left brain, and the six feathers represent the brain stem, which comprises 12 lines of the cranial nerves. The center of the wing connection is the thalamus, which corresponds to the hypothalamus and relates to Chakra 6. The staff core represents the spinal cord, and the five intersections of the two snakes represent Chakra 5, Chakra 4, Chakra 3, Chakra 2, and Chakra 1, respectively in Fig1. The two snakes, one red and one white, represent sexual feature corresponding to men and women hormones, respectively.

Therefore, the data described above reasonably suggests that the 7 chakras and the Caduceus symbol resemble and may have been related to the nervous systems because the most activity in the human body controlled by the nervous system.

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Conflict of interest

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Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally to this work and approved it for publication. T. M. (1). and A. S., designed the study. T. M. (1), performs the main experiments. T. M (1), K. Y., I. R., and M. J., prepared the manuscript in the study. T. M. (2), R. K., P. R., W.H., and T. P were instructed the experiment. The detailed discussion was made among ten.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

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APPENDICES - A

Fig 1. The comparison of the Chakras system, Nervous system and the Caduceus symbol.